

127 kg available NPK/ha. Farmyard manure (FYM) (0.562% N, 0.13% P, 0.75% K) was applied on a dry weight basis at 5 t/ha as an organic source for the main field only. Azospirillum was applied as a biofertilizer at 2 kg/800 m² of nursery area and at 2 kg/ha for the main field. P and K were applied,

per soil test recommendation, at 2.2 and 120 kg/ha, respectively, uniformly to all plots. N at four levels (see table) was applied as 50% basal and the remainder in equal splits at active tillering and panicle initiation.

The effect on yield of biofertilizer and organic manure either individually or in

combination was not significant, but in the subplots, N level was significant. N applied per soil test recommendation (98 kg N/ha) recorded significantly higher grain yield (4.3 t/ha) than the other treatments (see table) and a 30% yield increase over the control (3.3 t/ha). □

Sodicity-induced morphological disorder in rice laminae

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Soils having pH 7.4, 9.4, 9.8, and 10.0 were achieved by saturating sieved dry soil of pH 7.4 with different concentrations of sodium bicarbonate solution. The saturated soil was

subjected to repeated cycles of drying and wetting for 2 mo and then potted.

We planted 35-d-old seedlings of rice variety T3 in the pots. About 30 d after transplanting, white bands started appearing in the upper 1/3 portion of the first to third laminae from the top in plants growing at pH 10.0 (see figure). The white portion collapsed and the affected part withered. The symptoms were minor in some tillers at pH 9.8 and were not found at pH 7.4 and 9.4.

Laminae with symptoms at pH 10.0

were separated into 1/3 affected and 2/3 healthy parts. Laminae without symptoms at pH 7.4 were separated into upper 1/3 and lower 2/3 parts. Samples in three replications were analyzed for Na, K, Ca, and Mg content.

Laminae at pH 7.4 showed almost uniform Na content in upper 1/3 and lower 2/3 parts, but K content was more than double in the lower 2/3 (see table). Ca and Mg were higher in the upper part.

Laminae at pH 10.0 showed increased Na and Mg content, but K and Ca decreased. Distribution between the two parts was similar for Ca and Mg, but Na⁺ was less in the upper 1/3. K content did not show marked differences in the two parts. It is difficult to say whether such localized chlorosis, followed by withering, at higher sodicity is a cause or effect of marked change in distribution of K between the upper 1/3 and lower 2/3 of laminae. □

Healthy and chlorotic laminae from rice plants growing at pH 7.4 and 10.0. CSSRI, Karnal, India.

Elemental composition of upper (U) 1/3 and lower (L) 2/3 of healthy and affected laminae of rice variety T3 growing in sodic and nonsodic soils. CSSRI, Karnal, India.

pH	Percent dry weight							
	Na		K		Ca		Mg	
	U1/3	L2/3	U1/3	L2/3	U1/3	L2/3	U1/3	L2/3
7.4	0.05	0.04	1.07	2.26	0.38	0.24	0.37	0.32
10.0	0.82	0.96	0.70	0.72	0.29	0.22	0.54	0.45

Effect of fineness and time of pyrites application on rice yield and alkali soil properties

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The efficiency of using pyrites to reclaim alkali soils depends upon sulfur transformation, which is influenced by the fineness of the pyrites and the time allowed for oxidation before mixing into the soil. We studied the effect of 3 degrees of fineness (<3, 3-5, and 5-10 mm) and 3 times (0, 1, and 2 wk before transplanting) of application. The experiment was a factorial randomized block design with four replications.

The alkali soil in Awagarh, Uttar Pradesh, had a loamy texture with initial pH 9.2, EC 1.4 dS/m, 38% exchangeable Na, hydraulic conductivity 0.019 cm/h, and 2.0% CaCO₃ for the surface 0-15 cm soil. Pyrites containing 22% S (4 t/ha) was applied at field moisture capacity. It was broadcast, mixed in the top 10-12 cm soil, and good quality tubewell water ponded for 1 wk to leach down soluble salts. Seedlings of 35-d-old Jaya rice were transplanted. Recommended agronomic practices were followed. Increasing pyrites fineness to 3 mm and allowing 1 wk before mixing pyrites into the soil increased yields significantly (see table). Applying 5-mm pyrites 1 wk before mixing into alkali soils was most efficient for reclamation. □

Effect of fineness and time of application of pyrites on rice yield and reclamation of alkali soil of Awagarh, Uttar Pradesh.

	Yield		Soil (0-15 cm) characteristics after rice				
	Grain (t/ha)	Straw (t/ha)	pH ₂	EC ₂ (dS/m)	ESP	HC (cm/h)	CaCO ₃ (%)
Pyrites fineness (mm)							
<3	3.58	6.40	8.40	.61	21	.067	0.68
3-5	3.34	5.28	8.57	.65	25	.064	1.01
5-10	2.71	5.00	8.86	.90	30	.034	1.50
Time (wk before mixing into soil)							
0	2.84	4.85	8.76	.83	29	.042	1.18
1	3.45	6.24	8.53	.71	24	.062	1.00
2	3.34	5.84	8.50	.64	23	.067	1.00
CD (0.05) for fineness or application time	0.42	0.88	0.09	0.10	3	.08	0.22

Response of rice to input factors in farmers' fields

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Rice response to three input factors — variety, plant population, and fertilizer — was studied in farmers' fields during 1985 kharif (wet season) at five locations using a randomized complete block design with three replications. The varieties tested were IR6 (local) and

Yield gap and percentage contribution of individual input factors. D.I. Khan, Pakistan, 1985 kharif.

Yield response of rice to input factors in farmers' fields. Pakistan 1985 kharif.^a

Level ^b of input factors			Yield (t/ha)
Variety	Plant population	Fertilizer	
F	F	F	3.4
R	F	F	4.4
F	R	F	4.3
R	R	F	5.4
F	F	R	4.4
R	F	R	4.6
F	R	R	5.0
R	R	R	6.5
LSD (.05)			1.4
(.01)			1.9

^aAV of 5 locations, 3 replications. ^bF = farmers' practice, R = recommended practice.

KS282 (improved). Plant populations were 125,000 and 250,000 hills/ha, and fertilizer rates were 75-22 and 120-40 kg NP/ha. All P and 50% N were applied before transplanting, and the remaining N was topdressed 30 d after transplanting. All other recommended cultural practices were followed.

The highest yield (6.5 t/ha) was produced by all recommended inputs,

followed by recommended variety and plant population (see table). The yield gap — 3.1 t/ha — was significant (see figure). Low plant population was the main constraint to high rice yield. □

N fertilizer (urea) topdressed on unsaturated soil and deep-placed using reflooding water

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We evaluated a simple, practical, and efficient technique for deep placement of urea topdressed in irrigated ricefields. The technique combined N fertilizer application with soil moisture control.

Urea was topdressed on drained ricefields and the fields reflooded immediately. The fertilizer was deep-placed in the reduced zone by the infiltrating water.

The experiment was laid out in a clay loam soil, pH 6.2, 3.28% organic matter, 0.22% total N, 0.06% total P, and 2.01% total K. Fertilizer N efficiency was substantially increased compared with conventional broadcasting of N fertilizer on flooded ricefields (see table). □